

Dinoflagellate cyst biostratigraphy of the Bathonian, Callovian, and the Upper Jurassic in North Bulgaria

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(Published based upon unfinished manuscript of the authors: August 2022)

Abstract. Forty-four selected organic-walled dinoflagellate cyst species have been used for biozonation of the Bathonian, Callovian, and the Upper Jurassic in North Bulgaria. The dinocysts were collected from 49 borehole sections and two exposures. The following dinocyst zones are herein introduced and described: *Lithodinium valensii*–*Gongylocladus erymnoteichos* Concurrent-range Zone (lower–middle Bathonian); *Ellipsoidictyon reticulatum* Assemblage Zone (upper Bathonian–lower Callovian); *Dingodinium harsveldtii* Taxon-range Zone (middle–upper Callovian); *Lambodinium absidatum* Assemblage Zone (lower Oxfordian); *Scriniodinium dictyotum papillatum*–*Caddasphaera halosa* Concurrent-range Zone (middle–upper Oxfordian); *Rhyncodiniopsis gongylos* Assemblage Zone (lower Kimmeridgian); *Systematophora varispinosa*–*Gonyaulacysta? crassicornuta* Concurrent-range Zone (middle–upper Kimmeridgian); *Edmontodinium polyplacophorum* Assemblage Zone (lower Tithonian); and *Leptodinium? plagatum*–*Prolixosphaeridium perforospineum* Concurrent-range Zone (middle–upper Tithonian). Some of the zones were partly or completely subdivided in subzones. The dinocyst zones and subzones were correlated with the Bulgarian ammonite and calpionellid zones and subzones.

Dodekova, L., Sapunov, I. 2022. Dinoflagellate cyst biostratigraphy of the Bathonian, Callovian, and the Upper Jurassic in North Bulgaria. *Geologica Balcanica* 51 (2), 37–47.

Keywords: Jurassic, dinocyst stratigraphy, biozonation, North Bulgaria.

PREFACE

If they were alive today, Lilia Dodekova would be 88 and Ivo Sapunov would be 90. Regrettably, these two outstanding scholars in the Bulgarian Jurassic geology, who were a tandem in both science and life, left this world. However, their rich scientific legacy laid a solid foundation for future generations of their followers. The present paper is based upon an unpublished manuscript of Ivo Sapunov. He believed that this contribution would fill a sensible gap in the Bulgarian Jurassic biostratigraphic literature. The original ideas and understanding of the authors have been preserved to the maximum possible extent, and there is only a limited technical work in the final preparation of the manuscript for publica-

tion. In this way, the Editorial Board of *Geologica Balcanica* pays a tribute to our colleagues, who for many years were closely associated with our journal as authors, and Ivo Sapunov also as an editor. They will both be greatly missed.

Lubomir Metodiev, Silviya Petrova

INTRODUCTION

One of us (L. Dodekova) has been bounded up more than three decades in the study of the Jurassic dinoflagellate cysts in Bulgaria. The opportunity for both of us to be involved in the study of the subsurface Jurassic strata of the Moesian Platform came about

because of the active prospecting for fossil fuels that took place from the mid-1970s until the end of the 1980s. It is fortunate that the drilled sediments of the Bathonian, the Callovian, and the Upper Jurassic yielded abundant and well-preserved dinocysts, whereas these fossils were known to be extremely rare in the Jurassic outcrops. This allowed the borehole sections to be well-dated and correlated between each other. On the other hand, it was possible to obtain enough fossil material, so that the dinoflagellate cysts to be studied in more details from taxonomic point of view and its stratigraphic distribution to be well documented. The biostratigraphic potential of the dinocysts has not been used to date in this country, and the zonal subdivisions made herein are the first attempt in this respect for Bulgaria.

This work is based on the results of the papers published by Dodekova (1968, 1969, 1971, 1974, 1975, 1983), that were mainly taxonomically directed. In three more papers, the taxonomy of the Bulgarian Jurassic dinoflagellate cysts was summarized in accordance to their stratigraphic occurrence, *i.e.*, the dinocysts from the Bathonian and the Callovian (Dodekova *in*: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavka,

1990), the dinocysts from the Oxfordian and the Kimmeridgian (Dodekova, 1992), and the dinocysts from the Tithonian (Dodekova, 1994). In each paper, respective range-charts of the dinocyst taxa of the species group were given. Author's intention (Dodekova *in*: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavka, 1990, p. 5) to publish a fourth paper with a biostratigraphic synthesis was declared, but for various reasons, this did not happen. The empirical basis of this summary is the rich fossil material that has been collected from more than 70 borehole sections and a few key-outcrops (Fig. 1). This material enabled 230 dinocyst species to be determined. In succession, 85 species were described and figured by Dodekova (*in*: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavka, 1990), another 87 species were published by Dodekova (1992), and 58 species were also made known by Dodekova (1994). The stratigraphic ranges of these species were shown in three range-charts (Dodekova *in*: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavka, 1990, fig. 2; Dodekova, 1992, fig. 2; Dodekova, 1994, fig. 3). For the purpose of this work, 44 species were found to be suitable to create a zonation. They were collected from samples of 49 borehole sections and 2 outcrops (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Simplified tectonic map of Bulgaria (after Dabovski and Zagorchev, 2009) showing the localities and borehole sections that yielded the dinocysts for this study, marked by a dot and a number: **1** – locality Belogradchik; **2** – borehole R-1 Byalo Pole; **3** – boreholes R-3 and R-12 Chiren; **4** – borehole R-10 Golyamo Peshtene; **5** – borehole R-7 Varbitsa; **6** – borehole R-1 Knezha; **7, 8** – boreholes R-1 and R-5 Dolni Dabnik; **9** – borehole R-1 Trastenik; **10** – borehole R-1 Gigen; **11** – borehole R-3 Brest; **12** – borehole R-2 Dabovan; **13** – borehole R-2 Grivitsa; **14** – borehole R-1 Slavyanovo; **15–18** – boreholes R-3, R-4 and R-8 Devetaki, R-1 Brestovo; **19** – borehole R-2hg Ovcha Mogila; **20** – locality Mahala Popska; **21** – borehole R-1 Chereshevo; **22** – borehole R-2 Preslavtsi; **23** – borehole S-11 Hitrino; **24** – borehole S-24 Sultantsi; **25** – borehole S-21 Kalugeritsa; **26** – borehole S-24 Nikola Kozlevo; **27** – boreholes S-33 and S-33 Esenitsa; **28** – borehole R-16h Orlyak; **29** – borehole S-32 Dolina; **30** – borehole S-12 Gornyak; **31** – borehole R-9 Kardam; **32** – borehole S-10 Chernookovo; **33–38** – boreholes R-87 Gurkovo, R-57, R-67 and R-140A Makedonka, R-109 Vranino, R-55 Konare, R-53 Belgun; **39** – boreholes R-1 and R-3 Tyulenovo; **40–42** – boreholes R-9 Bozvelyisko, R-1 Hrabrino, R-5 Tutrakantsi; **43–47** – boreholes R-1, R-2 and R-8 Sultantsi, R-10 Padina, R-11 Zhitnitsa; **48–51** – boreholes R-1, R-3 and R-4 Yunak, R-14 Grozdyovo (after Dodekova, 1992, 1994).

Moesian Platform units (a–g): a) Vidin-Strehaya Dome; b) Lom Depression; c) Iskar-Yantra Step; d) Alexandria Depression; e) North Bulgarian Dome; f) southern slope of the Dobrogea Massif; g) South Moesian Platform Slope; h, i) South Carpathian orogen: h) Kraina Unit; i) Kula Unit; j–l) Balkan orogen units: j) West Balkan Unit; k) Fore-Balkan Unit; l) East Balkan Unit.

Biostratigraphic contributions of Lilia Dodekova on the Middle and Upper Jurassic dinoflagellates, widely used throughout the world, could also be important for correlation of the Upper Jurassic to Berriasian in the Tethyan and Boreal biogeographic provinces (see Colpaert *et al.*, 2017) since ammonites and calpionellids are not applicable for this purpose.

THE BATHONIAN AND CALLOVIAN DINOFLAGELLATE CYST ZONES AND SUBZONES

Based on the Bulgarian material available, three types of dinoflagellate cyst zones and subzones were distinguished: taxon–range zones and subzones, concurrent–range zones and subzones and assemblage zones and subzones. We follow the rules of the International Stratigraphic Guide, according to which: 1) “A taxon–range zone is the body of strata representing the known range of occurrence (stratigraphic and geographic) of specimens of a particular taxon (species, genus, family, etc.). It is the sum of the documented occurrences in all individual sections on which the particular taxon has been identified” (Salvador, 1994, p. 57); 2) “A concurrent–range zone is the body of strata including the concurrent coincidence of the range zones of two specified taxa. Other taxa may be included as characterizing members of the zone, but only two can be used for defining the boundaries” (Salvador, 1994, p. 58); and 3) “An assemblage zone is a body of strata characterized by a distinctive assemblage or association of three or more fossil taxa taken together distinguishes in biostratigraphic character from adjacent strata. However, marine planktonic fossil assemblages may approach worldwide extent” (Salvador, 1994, pp. 62, 63). The Bulgarian dinoflagellate cyst assemblage zones and subzones correspond both to the “multi–taxon concurrent–range zones” and the “Oppel–zones”, previously used in the Stratigraphic Guide (Hedberg, 1976, pp. 55, 57, figs 6, 8) and currently included in the extent of an assemblage zone.

Lithodinia valensii–*Gonyolodinium erymnoteichos* Concurrent–range Zone

Name. The zone is named after the species with coincident occurrences that define it (see Fig. 2).

Stratigraphy. This zone is defined by the coincident range of occurrence of *Lithodinia valensii* (Sarjeant, 1966) Lentin & Williams, 1977 (Dodekova, *in*: Tchou-

matchenko and Černjavská 1990, p. 15, pl. 9, fig. 13), and *Gonyolodinium erymnoteichos* Fenton, Neves & Piel, 1980 (Dodekova, 1990, p. 27, pl. 3, fig. 10). The *L. valensii*–*G. erymnoteichos* Concurrent–range Zone matches with the lower and middle Bathonian and corresponds to the total extent of the Bathonian ammonite zones, from the *Gonolkites convergens* Zone to the *Morrisiceras morrisi* Zone (*sensu* Metodiev and Sapunov (2017) (see Fig. 3).

Distribution. The occurrence of *Lithodinia valensii* was documented in five borehole sections: R-1 Dolni Dabnik (depth 2720 m, Polaten Formation, lower Bathonian); R-16h Orlyak (depth 797 m, Esenitsa Formation, middle Bathonian); S-31 Esenitsa (depth 779 m, Esenitsa Formation, middle Bathonian); S-33 Esenitsa (depth 784.8–805 m, Esenitsa Formation, lower–middle Bathonian); and S-21 Kalugeritsa (depth 904 m, Esenitsa Formation, middle Bathonian). *Gonyolodinium erymnoteichos* was found in one exposure near the town of Belogradchik (Polaten Formation, upper part, lower Bathonian), as well as in two borehole sections: R-1 Chereshevo (depth 1128.5–1130 m, Esenitsa Formation, middle Bathonian); and R-7 Varbitsa (depth 3604 m,

Bathonian			Callovian			Dinocyst species
Lower	Middle	Upper	Lower	Middle	Upper	
						<i>Lithodinia valensii</i>
						<i>Gonyolodinium erymnoteichos</i>
						<i>Kylindrocysta spinosa</i>
						<i>Ellipsoidictyon reticulatum</i>
						<i>Tabulodinium senarium</i>
						<i>Lithodinia insulofigurata</i>
						<i>Belodinium obsoletum</i>
						<i>Tubotuberella cf. rombiformis</i>
						<i>Lithodinia cf. superornata</i>
						<i>Lithodinia A sp.</i>
						<i>Cleistosphaeridium varispinosum</i>
						<i>Sentusidinium baculatum</i>
						<i>Scriniolodinium cf. luridum</i>
						<i>Chytroisphaeridia scabrata</i>
						<i>Dingodinium harsveldtii</i>
						<i>Polygonifera? aspera</i>
						<i>Pareodinia barentsensis</i>
						<i>Eodinia cf. pachytheca</i>

Fig. 2. Range-chart of the Bulgarian Bathonian and Callovian dinoflagellate cyst species.

Stage	Substage	Ammonite Zones	Dinocyst Zones	Dinocyst Subzones	
Callovian	Upper	<i>Pseudopeltoceras</i> – <i>Peltomorphites athletoides</i> Interval Zone	<i>Dingodinium harsveldtii</i> Taxon-range Zone	<i>Polygonifera? aspera</i> Assemblage Subzone	
	Middle	<i>Hecticoceras</i> spp.			
	Lower	<i>Macrocephalites gracilis</i>	<i>Ellipsoidictyon reticulatum</i> Assemblage Zone	<i>Scriniodinium</i> cf. <i>luridum</i> – <i>Chytroeisphaeridia scabrata</i> Concurrent-range Subzone	
<i>Macrocephalites herveyi</i>					
Upper	<i>Clydoniceras discus</i>	<i>Ellipsoidictyon reticulatum</i> Assemblage Zone			<i>Clistosphaeridium varispinosum</i> – <i>Sentusidinium baculatum</i> Concurrent-range Subzone
	<i>Oxycerites oppeli</i>				
	<i>Procerites hodsoni</i>				
Middle	<i>Morrisiceras morrisi</i>	<i>Lithodinium valensii</i> – <i>Gongylocladus erymnoteichos</i> Concurrent-range Zone			<i>Kylindrocysta spinosa</i> Taxon-range Subzone
	<i>Tulites subcontractus</i>				
	<i>Procerites progracilis</i>				
Lower	<i>Siemiradzkiella repljanensis</i>		<i>Lithodinium valensii</i> – <i>Gongylocladus erymnoteichos</i> Concurrent-range Zone	<i>Kylindrocysta spinosa</i> Taxon-range Subzone	
	<i>Morphoceras macrescens</i>				
	<i>Gonolkites convergens</i>				

Fig. 3. Correlation between the Bulgarian ammonite zones of the Bathonian and Callovian and the dinoflagellate cyst zones and subzones introduced herein.

Gorno Belotintsi Member of the Bov Formation, middle Bathonian).

***Kylindrocysta spinosa* Taxon-range Subzone**

Name. This subzone is named after the defining taxon.

Stratigraphy. The subzone is defined by the known range of occurrence of *Kylindrocysta spinosa* Fenton, Neves & Piel, 1980 (Dodekova *in*: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990, p. 13, pl. 2, fig. 7) (see Fig. 2). It corresponds to the middle Bathonian and correlates with the total extent of three ammonite zones, from the *Procerites progracilis* Zone to the *Morrisiceras morrisi* Zone (Metodiev and Sapunov, 2017; see also Fig. 3).

Distribution. The index-species was found in two borehole sections: R-16h Orlyak (depth 779–784 m,

Esenitsa Formation, middle Bathonian); and R-1 Chershovo (depth 1128.8–1130 m, Esenitsa Formation, middle Bathonian).

***Ellipsoidictyon reticulatum* Assemblage Zone**

Name. *Ellipsoidictyon reticulatum* is chosen as an index, since it is a species of well-known occurrence in North-west Europe and Morocco that coincides to a certain extent with the stratigraphic range of its representatives in Bulgaria (Fauconnier, 1997, pp. 230, 235, tables 33, 37).

Stratigraphy. The zone is defined by the approximate coincidence of ranges of seven dinocyst species: *Ellipsoidictyon reticulatum* (Valensi, 1953) Lentin & Williams, 1977 (Dodekova *in*: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990, p. 12, pl. 1, figs 4, 5); *Tabu-*

lodinium senarium Dodekova in: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990 (p. 24, pl. 4, figs 4–10; pl. 9, figs 3–5, 9, 10); *Lithodinia insulofigurata* (Dodekova, 1975) Lentin & Williams, 1977 (Dodekova in: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990, p. 15, pl. 10, fig. 10); *Belodinium obsoletum* Dodekova, 1975 (Dodekova in: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990, p. 7, pl. 10, fig. 1); *Tubotuberella* cf. *rombiformis* Vozzhennikova, 1967 ex Stover & Evitt, 1978 (Dodekova, 1990, p. 33, pl. 6, fig. 6); *Lithodinia* cf. *superornata* (W. Wetzel, 1967) Fenton, 1981 (Dodekova in: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990, p. 15, pl. 3, fig. 4).

The *E. reticulatum* Assemblage Zone corresponds to the upper Bathonian and the lower Callovian and correlates with the total extent of the ammonite zones, from the *Procerites hodsoni* Zone (Metodieff and Sapunov, 2017) to the *Macrocephalites gracilis* Zone (Metodieff and Sapunov, 2019) (see Fig. 3).

Distribution. *Ellipsoidictyon reticulatum* was found in two borehole sections: S-12 Gornjak (depth 852.2 m, Dobrich Formation, lower Callovian), and S-10 Chernookovo (depth 944.6–949 m, Dobrich Formation, upper Bathonian). Dinocysts specimens of *Tabulodinium senarium* were discovered in three borehole sections: S-12 Gornjak (depth 852.2 m, Dobrich Formation, lower Callovian); R-87 Gurkovo (depth 1371.3 m, Dobrich Formation, upper Bathonian); and R-1 Tyulenovo (depth 1017.4 m, Dobrich Formation, upper Bathonian). Specimens of *Lithodinia insulofigurata* were determined from samples of three borehole sections: S-10 Chernookovo (depth 946–948 m, Dobrich Formation, upper Bathonian); S-33 Esenitsa (depth 778.5 m, Esenitsa Formation, ?upper Bathonian); and R-109 Vranino (depth 1315.5 m, Dobrich Formation, upper Bathonian–lower Callovian).

Representatives of *Belodinium obsoletum* were found in the borehole sections studied by Dodekova (1975, p. 24), as well as in six more boreholes: R-9 Septemvriyski (depth 3686 m, Verenitsa Member of the Bov Formation, lower Callovian); R-14 Grozdovo (depth 2679 m, Polaten Formation, upper Bathonian/lower Callovian); R-1 Yunak (depth 1746.5 m, Polaten Formation, upper Bathonian); R-3 Yunak (depth 1702.2 m, Polaten Formation, lower Callovian, together with *Macrocephalites* spp.); R-1 Tyulenovo (depth 1010 m, Dobrich Formation, upper Bathonian); and R-67 Makedonka (depth 1375.7 m, Dobrich Formation, upper Bathonian).

The presence of *Tubotuberella* cf. *rombiformis* was recorded in three borehole sections: S-12 Gornjak (depth 852.2 m, Dobrich Formation, ?lower

Callovian); S-54 Gurkovo (depth 1332 m, Dobrich Formation, upper Bathonian); and R-1 Tyulenovo (depth 1017.4 m, Dobrich Formation, upper Bathonian). Cysts of *Lithodinia* cf. *superornata* were found in four borehole sections: R-1 Yunak (depth 1746.5 m, Polaten Formation, upper Bathonian–lower Callovian); R-3 Yunak (depth 1702.2 m, Polaten Formation, lower Callovian); R-6 Sultantsi (depth 1960 m, Esenitsa Formation, upper Bathonian); and R-8 Sultantsi (depth 1977.5 m, Esenitsa Formation, upper Bathonian).

The last element of the zonal association is *Lithodinia* sp. A that was determined on specimens, collected from three borehole sections: R-67 Makedonka (depth 1370.8 m, Dobrich Formation, upper Bathonian); S-11 Hitrino (depth 890 m, Drinovo Formation, lower Callovian); and S-12 Gornjak (depth 852.2 m, Dobrich Formation, ?lower Callovian).

***Cleistosphaeridium varispinosum*–*Sentusidinium baculatum* Concurrent–range Subzone**

Name. The subzone is named after the species with coincident occurrences that define it (see Fig. 2).

Stratigraphy. This subzone is defined by the coincident occurrence ranges of *Cleistosphaeridium varispinosum* (Sarjeant, 1959) Woollam & Riding, 1983 (Dodekova in: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990, p. 9, pl. 2, fig. 6), and *Sentusidinium baculatum* (Dodekova, 1975) Sarjeant & Stover, 1978 (Dodekova in: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990, p. 17, pl. 7, figs 13, 14).

The *C. varispinosum*–*S. baculatum* Concurrent–range Subzone corresponds to the upper Bathonian and correlates with the total extent of three ammonite zones, from the *Procerites hodsoni* Zone to the *Clydoniceras discus* Zone (Metodieff and Sapunov, 2017; see also Fig. 3).

Distribution. *Cleistosphaeridium varispinosum* was found in abundance in borehole section R-1 Tyulenovo (depth 1017.4, Dobrich Formation, upper Bathonian). Numerous specimens of *Sentusidinium baculatum* were recorded in two borehole sections: R-54 Gurkovo (depth 1341 m, Dobrich Formation, upper Bathonian); and S-33 Esenitsa (depth 778.3 m, Esenitsa Formation, upper Bathonian).

***Scriniodinium* cf. *luridum*–*Chytroeisphaeridia scabrata* Concurrent–range Subzone**

Name. This subzone is named after the species with coincident occurrences that define it (see Fig. 2).

Stratigraphy. The subzone is characterized by the coincident occurrence ranges of *Scriniodinium* cf.

luridum (Deflandre, 1933) Klement, 1960 *sensu* Riding *et al.*, 1985 (Dodekova *in*: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990, p. 31, pl. 5, fig. 2), and *Chytroeisphaeridia scabrata* Pockock, 1972 (Dodekova *in*: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990, p. 26, pl. 10, figs 9, 11). It corresponds to the lower Callovian, and correlates with the *Macrocephalites herveyi* and *Macrocephalites gracilis* zones (Metodiev and Sapunov, 2019; see also Fig. 3).

Distribution. The dinoflagellate cysts of *Scriniodium cf. luridum* were found in one borehole section: R-1 Byalo Pole (depth 3387 m, Verenitsa Member of the Bov Formation, lower Callovian, in association with *Macrocephalites sp. indet.*). Specimens of *Chytroeisphaeridia scabrata* were recorded in the borehole section S-12 Gornyak (depth 852.2, Dobrich Formation, ?lower Callovian).

Dingodinium harsveldtii Taxon–range Zone

Name. The zone is named after *D. harsveldtii* whose stratigraphic distribution defines it.

Stratigraphy. The known range of occurrence of *Dingodinium harsveldtii* Herngreen *et al.*, 1984 (Dodekova *in*: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990, p. 12, pl. 1, figs 8, 9) characterize the zone. It corresponds to the middle and the upper Callovian, and correlates with the total extent of the *Hectoceras* spp. Zone and the *Pseudopeltoceras–Peltomorphites athletoides* Interval Zone (Metodiev and Sapunov, *unpubl.*; see Fig. 3).

Distribution. The index-species was found in four borehole sections: R-3 Chiren (depth 1292–1293.5 m, Yavorets Formation, middle and upper Callovian), R-1 Bardarski Geran (depth 3188 m, Verenitsa Member of the Bov Formation, middle Callovian), R-7 Sultantsi (depth 1895 m, Yavorets Formation, upper Callovian), and R-1 Hrabrovo (depth 1977.2 m, Yavorets Formation, middle Callovian).

Polygonifera? aspera Assemblage Subzone

Name. The name of the subzone is after *Polygonifera? aspera*, as this species was recorded in great number of specimens in borehole section R-1 Hrabrovo.

Stratigraphy. The subzone is characterized by the approximate coincidence of the ranges of three dinocyst species: *Polygonifera? aspera* Dodekova *in*: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990 (p. 40, pl. 4, figs 3, 11–16), *Eodinia cf. pachytheca* Eisenack, 1936 emended Gocht 1975 (Dodekova *in*: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990, p. 37, pl. 9, fig. 7), and *Pareodinia barentsensis* Smelror, 1988 (Dode-

kova *in*: Tchoumatchenko and Černjavská, 1990, p. 22, pl. 10, fig. 15) (see Fig. 2).

Distribution. The index-species was found to compose about 50% of the middle Callovian dinocyst association in the borehole section R-1 Hrabrovo (depth 1977.2 m, Yavorets Formation). It was also found in the borehole section R-7 Sultantsi (depth 1896 m, Yavorets Formation, middle Callovian). In addition, two borehole sections yielded examples of *Eodinia cf. pachytheca*: R-1 Bardarski Geran (depth 3185–3188 m, Verenitsa Member of the Bov Formation, middle Callovian); and R-1 Hrabrovo (depth 1977.2 m, Yavorets Formation, middle Callovian). *Pareodinia barentsensis* was recorded in the borehole section R-1 Hrabrovo (depth 1977.2 m, Yavorets Formation, middle Callovian).

THE OXFORDIAN DINOFLAGELLATE CYST ZONES

Limbodinium absidatum Assemblage Zone

Name. The name of the zone derives from *Limbodinium absidatum*, a species that displayed the most abundant occurrence regarding the rest of the zonal association.

Stratigraphy. The zone is defined by the approximate coincidence of the ranges of occurrence of four dinocyst species: *Limbodinium absidatum* (Drugg, 1978) Riding, 1987 (Dodekova, 1992, p. 63, pl. 9, fig. 8), *Ringaudella apiculata* (Cookson & Eisenack, 1960) *sensu* Below, 1982 (Dodekova, 1992, p. 47,

Oxfordian			Kimmeridgian			Dinocyst species
Lower	Middle	Upper	Lower	Middle	Upper	
						<i>Limbodinium absidatum</i>
						<i>Ringaudella apiculata</i>
						<i>Cleistosphaeridium lumectum</i>
						<i>Stephanelytron sp. aff. redeliffense</i>
						<i>Scriniodium dictyotum papillatum</i>
						<i>Caddasphaera halosa</i>
						<i>Rhynchodiniopsis gongylos</i>
						<i>Hystrichodinium? lanceatum</i>
						<i>Leptodinium cf. ambiguum</i>
						<i>Gochteodinia verrucosa</i>
						<i>Systematophora varispinosa</i>
						<i>Gonyaulacysta? crassicornuta</i>

Fig. 4. Range-chart of the Bulgarian Oxfordian and Kimmeridgian dinoflagellate cyst species.

pl. 6, fig. 1), *Stephanelytron* sp. aff. *redeliffense* Sarjeant, 1961 (Dodekova, 1992, p. 49, pl. 9., figs 5, 7, 10), and *Cleistosphaeridium lumectum* (Sarjeant, 1960) Davey *et al.*, 1969 (Dodekova, 1992, p. 40, pl. 1, fig. 8) (see Fig. 4). The *Limbodinium absidatum* Assemblage Zone corresponds to the lower Oxfordian and correlates to the total extent of

the *Peltomorphites athletoides* and the *Creniceras renggeri* ammonite zones (see Fig. 5).

Distribution. Five borehole sections yielded specimens of *Limbodinium absidatum*: S-32 Dolina (depth 743 m, Chernookovo Formation, lower Oxfordian, associated with ammonites of the index-species of *C. renggeri* Zone); S-9 Kardam (depth 878 m, Cher-

Stage	Substage	Ammonite Zones and Subzones	Calpionellid Zones	Dinocyst Zones	Dinocyst Subzones
Tithonian	Upper	<i>P. trans.</i> Z. <i>Malbosciceras chaperi</i> Sz. <i>H. (M.) microcanthus</i> Sz.	<i>Calpionella</i> Z.	<i>Leptodinium? plagatum</i> – <i>Prolixosphaeridium perforaspineum</i> Concurrent-range Zone	<i>Prolixosphaeridium? foratum</i> – <i>Dichadogonyaulax culmula</i> Concurrent-range Subzone
			<i>Crassicollaria</i> Z.		
	Middle	<i>Parapallasiceras</i> spp. Z. <i>Virgatosimoceras rothpletzi</i> Z.	<i>Chitinoidella</i> Z.		<i>Occisucysta balios</i> – <i>Lithodinia bulloidea</i> Concurrent-range Subzone
	Lower	<i>Franconites vimineus</i> Z. <i>Subplanitoides schwertschlaqeri</i> Z. <i>Hybonotoceras hybonotum</i> Z.			<i>Edmontodinium polyplacophorum</i> Assemblage Zone
Kimmeridgian	Upper	<i>Hybonotoceras beckeri</i> Z.		<i>Systematophora varispinosa</i> – <i>Gonyaulacysta? crassicornuta</i> Concurrent-range Zone	
	Middle	<i>Aspidoceras sesquinodosum</i> Z. <i>Crussoliceras</i> – <i>A. sesquinodosum</i> Z.			
		Lower	<i>Crussoliceras divisum</i> Z. <i>Ataxioceras</i> (A.) <i>hypselocyclum</i> Z. <i>Atax. (Parataxioceras) desmoides</i> Z.	<i>Rhynchodinopsis gongylos</i> Assemblage Zone	
	Oxfordian	Upper	<i>Idoceras planula</i> Z. <i>Epipeltoceras bimammatum</i> Z. <i>Perisph. (Dichotomoceras) bifurcatus</i> Z.		<i>Scriniodinium dictyotum papillatum</i> – <i>Caddasphaera halosa</i> Concurrent-range Zone
Middle			<i>Gregoryceras riazii</i> Z. <i>Perisph. (Dichotomosph.) antecessens</i> Z. <i>Perisph. (Dichotomosph.) episcopalis</i> Z.		
			Lower	<i>Creniceras renggeri</i> Z. <i>Peltomorphites athletoides</i> Z.	

Fig. 5. Correlation between the Bulgarian ammonite zones of the Oxfordian–Tithonian, calpionellid zones of the Tithonian–Berriasian and the dinoflagellate cyst zones and subzones introduced herein.

nookovo Formation, Lower Oxfordian); S-5 Tutrakantsi (depth 1756 m, Provadiya Formation, lower Oxfordian); and R-109 Vranino (depth 1298 m, Provadiya Formation, lower Oxfordian, associated with ammonites of *Neocampylites (N.) delmontatus* (Oppel, 1863), from the *Peltomorphites athletoides* Zone).

Dinoflagellate cysts of *Ringaudella apiculata* were found in the borehole section R-109 Vranino (depth 1298–1303 m, Provadiya Formation, lower Oxfordian, associated with ammonites of *Neocampylites (N.) delmontatus* (Oppel, 1863), recorded at depth of 1299 m, and *N. (N.) helveticus* (Jeannot, 1951), found at depth 1300 m). The examples of *Cleistosphaeridium lumectum* were determined on specimens from the borehole section S-9 Kardam (depth 877.5 m, Chernookovo Formation, lower Oxfordian).

***Scriniodinium dictyotum papillatum*–*Caddasphaera halosa* Concurrent–range Zone**

Name. The zone is named after the species with coincident occurrences that define it.

Stratigraphy. This zone is defined by the coincident concurrent ranges of *Scriniodinium dictyotum papillatum* Gitmetz, 1970 (Dodekova, 1992, p. 58, pl. 9, fig. 11), and *Caddasphaera halosa* (Filatoff, 1975) Fenton *et al.*, 1980 (Dodekova, 1992, p. 64, pl. 7, fig. 4). It corresponds to the middle and the upper Oxfordian and correlates with the total extent of six ammonite zones, from the *Perisphinctes (Dichotomosphinctes) episcopalis* Zone to the *Idoceras planula* Zone (see Fig. 5).

Distribution. Specimens of *Scriniodinium dictyotum papillatum* were found in two borehole sections: R-109 Vranino (depth 1291 m, Chernookovo Formation, upper Oxfordian, associated with an ammonite of the genus *Idoceras* at depth 1294 m, indicating the *I. planula* Zone); and S-10 Chernookovo (depth 933.2 m, Chernookovo Formation, middle–upper Oxfordian). The dinocysts of *Caddasphaera halosa* were recorded in the borehole section S-10 Chernookovo (depth 924–936 m, Chernookovo Formation, middle–upper Oxfordian).

THE KIMMERIDGIAN DINOFLAGELLATE CYST ZONES

***Rhyncodiniopsis gongylos* Assemblage Zone**

Name. The name of the zone derived from the dinoflagellate cyst species *Rhyncodiniopsis gongylos* that is the most widely distributed member of the zonal association.

Stratigraphy. This assemblage zone is defined by the approximate coincidence of the ranges of occurrence of four dinocyst species: *Rhyncodiniopsis gongylos* (Sarjeant, 1966) Sarjeant 1982 (Dodekova, 1992, p. 57, pl. 6, figs 12, 13), *Hystrichodinium? lanceatum* Davies, 1983 (Dodekova, 1992, p. 64, pl. 8, fig. 3), *Leptodinium cf. ambiguum* (Deflandre, 1939) Helenes 1984 (Dodekova, 1992, p. 55, pl. 7, fig. 3), and *Gochteodinia verrucosa* (Vozzhennikova, 1967) Dörhöfer & Davies, 1980 (Dodekova, 1992, p. 51, pl. 6, fig. 3) (see Fig. 4). The zone corresponds to the lower Kimmeridgian and correlates with the total extent of three ammonite zones, from the *Ataxioceras (Parataxioceras) desmoides* Zone to the *Crussoliceras divisum* Zone (Fig. 5).

Distribution. The index-species was recorded in two borehole sections: R-55 Konare (depth 1029 m, Chernookovo Formation, lower Kimmeridgian); and R-109 Vranino (depth 1289–1291 m, Chernookovo Formation, lower Kimmeridgian). *Hystrichodinium? lanceatum* was determined on specimens, collected from the borehole section R-55 Konare (depth 1035 m, Chernookovo Formation, lower Kimmeridgian).

The cysts of *Leptodinium cf. ambiguum* came from the borehole section R-140A Makedonka (Depth 1285 m, Chernookovo Formation, lower Kimmeridgian, in association with an ammonite of the genus *Crussoliceras*, from the *C. divisum* Zone, found at depth 1289.3 m). *Gochteodinia verrucosa* were recognized on specimens, collected from the borehole section R-109 Vranino (depth 1291.6 m, Chernookovo Formation, lower Kimmeridgian).

***Systematophora varispinosa*–*Gonyaulacysta? crassicornuta* Concurrent–range Zone**

Name. The zone is named after the species with coincident occurrences that define it.

Stratigraphy. This zone is characterized by the coincident concurrent ranges of *Systematophora varispinosa* Brenner, 1988 (Dodekova, 1992, p. 50, pl. 5, figs 8, 9), and *Gonyaulacysta? crassicornuta* (Klement, 1960) Sarjeant, 1969 emended Sarjeant, 1984 (Dodekova, 1992, p. 54, pl. 7, figs 9, 10). It conforms to the middle and the upper Kimmeridgian, and correlates with the total extent of three ammonite zones, from the *Crussoliceras–Ataxioceras sesquinodosum* Zone to the *Hybonotoceras beckeri* Zone (Fig. 5).

Distribution. The dinoflagellate cysts of *Systematophora varispinosa* were found in five borehole sections: R-2hg Ovcha Mogila (depth 1549 m,

Pleven Formation, Kimmeridgian); R-1 Slavyanovo (depth 1815 m, Kaspichan Formation, ?middle/upper Kimmeridgian); R-3 Brest (depth 1818.5 m, Kaspichan Formation, ?middle–upper Kimmeridgian); R-2 Grivitsa (depth 2385 m, Pleven Formation, ?middle–upper Kimmeridgian); and R-5 Dolni Dabnik (depth 2655–2658 m, Pleven Formation, ?middle–upper Kimmeridgian).

Gonyaulacysta? crassicornuta was recorded in two borehole sections: R2hg Ovcha Mogila (depth 1549 m, Pleven Formation, Kimmeridgian); and R-2 Dabovan (depth 1634.5 m, Kaspichan Formation, ?middle–upper Kimmeridgian).

THE TITHONIAN DINOFLAGELLATE CYST ZONES

Egmontodinium polyplacophorum Assemblage Zone

Name. *Egmontodinium polyplacophorum* was selected from five dinocyst species of diagnostic value of the assemblage as being of the greatest occurrence (see Fauconnier, 1997, p. 232, Table 34).

Stratigraphy. The zonal assemblage is defined by the approximate coincidence of ranges of the following species: *E. polyplacophorum* Gitmez & Sarjeant, 1972 (Dodekova, 1994, p. 22, pl. 3, figs 10, 14), *Cribroperidinium? globatum* (Gitmez & Sarjeant, 1972) Helenes, 1984 (Dodekova, 1994, p. 37, pl. 9, fig. 1), *Gochteodinia mutabilis* (Riley in Fisher & Riley, 1980) Davey, 1982 (Dodekova, 1994, p. 36), *Perisseiasphaeridium* cf. *ingegardii* Nøhr-Hansen, 1986 (Dodekova, 1994, p. 25, pl. 6, figs 2–4), and *Subtilisphaera? paeminosa* (Drugg, 1978) Bujak & Davies, 1983 (Dodekova, 1994, p. 33, pl. 3, figs 11, 15) (see Fig. 6). The *Egmontodinium polyplacophorum* Assemblage Zone conforms to the lower Tithonian and correlates with the total extent of the ammonite zones from the *Hybonoticerias hybonotum* Zone to the *Franconites vimineus* Zone (see Fig. 5).

Distribution. Two borehole sections yielded specimens of *E. polyplacophorum*: R-3 Yunak (depth 1756.4 m, Ticha Formation, lower Tithonian); and R-4 Yunak (depth 1651.5 m, Ticha Formation, lower Kimmeridgian). *Cribroperidinium? globatum* were found in two borehole sections: R-4 Devetaki (depth 2869–2871 m, Pleven Formation, lower Tithonian); and R-3 Yunak (depth 1756 m, Ticha Formation, lower Tithonian). One borehole yielded specimens of *Gochteodinia mutabilis*: R-4 Yunak (depth 1654.5 m, Ticha Forma-

tion, lower Tithonian). The borehole section R-9 Devetaki (depth 2328 m, Pleven Formation, lower Tithonian) yielded some specimens of *Perisseiasphaeridium* cf. *ingegardii*, but in fragmentary state of preservation. The dinoflagellate cysts of *Subtilisphaera? paeminosa* were recorded on specimens, collected from the borehole section R-4 Devetaki (depth 2869–2871 m, Pleven Formation, lower Tithonian).

Leptodinium? plagatum–Prolixosphaeridium perfospineum Concurrent–range Zone

Name. This zone is named after the two species with coincident occurrence whose ranges define it.

Stratigraphy. The coincident concurrent ranges of *Leptodinium? plagatum* Dodekova, 1994 (p. 41, pl. 11, figs 1–12, text-fig. 7), and *Prolixosphaeridium perfospineum* Dodekova, 1994 (p. 27, pl. 5, figs 2, 12, 16–18) characterize the zone (see Fig. 6). It corresponds to the middle and upper Tithonian, and probably the lowermost part of Berriasian and correlates with the total extent of the ammonite zonal succession from the *Virgatosimoceras rothpletzi* Zone to the *Paraulacosphinctes transitorius* Zone (see also Fig. 5).

Tithonian			Dinocyst species
Lower	Middle	Upper	
			<i>Egmontodinium polyplacophorum</i>
			<i>Cribroperidinium? globatum</i>
			<i>Gochteodinia mutabilis</i>
			<i>Perisseiasphaeridium</i> cf. <i>ingegardii</i>
			<i>Subtilisphaera? paeminosa</i>
			<i>Leptodinium? plagatum</i>
			<i>Prolixosphaeridium perfospineum</i>
			<i>Occiscyca balios</i>
			<i>Lithodinia bulloidea</i>
			<i>Systematophora daveyi</i>
			<i>Systematophora? prodigiosa</i>
			<i>Semicavidinium mitra</i>
			<i>Prolixosphaeridium? foratum</i>
			<i>Dichadogonyaulax culmula</i>
			<i>Leptodinium? ambiguiformis</i>
			<i>Cribroperidinium</i> sp. A

Fig. 6. Range-chart of the Bulgarian Tithonian dinoflagellate cyst species.

Distribution. Specimens of *Leptodinium?* *plagatum* were obtained from many borehole sections and one exposure: R-1 Dolni Dabnik (depth 2560.5 m, Pleven Formation, upper Tithonian); R-1 Stezherovo (depth 1523 m, Kaspichan Formation, upper Tithonian); R-1 Gigen (depth 1644 m, Kaspichan Formation, middle–upper Tithonian); R-3 Brest (depth 1747 m, Kaspichan Formation, middle–upper Tithonian); R-9 Bozvelyisko (depth 2302 m, Ticha Formation, upper Tithonian, in association with calpionellids from the *Crassicollaria* Zone); R-7 Sultantsi (depth 1707–1765 m, Ticha Formation, upper Tithonian, in association with calpionellids from the *Crassicollaria* Zone); R-11 Zhitnitsa (depth 1713.8 m, Ticha Formation, upper Tithonian–Berriasian, in association with calpionellids from the *Calpionella alpina* Subzone of the *Calpionella* Zone); R-1 Yunak (depth 1495–1578 m, Ticha Formation, upper Tithonian, in association with calpionellids from the *Crassicollaria* Zone, and an ammonite of *Himalaytes* (*Micracanthoceras*) *fraudator* (Zittel, 1868) that indicates the *H. (M.) microcanthus* Subzone of the *P. transitorius* Zone, at depth 1629–1641 m); R-3 Yunak (depth 1688–1695 m, Ticha Formation, uppermost middle Tithonian–lowermost upper Tithonian, in association with calpionellids from the *Chitinoidea* Zone); R-4 Yunak (depth 1629–1638.7 m, Ticha Formation, middle and upper Tithonian), and an outcrop near the Mahala Popska, town of Sevlievo (Zlataritsa–Cherniosum Formation, upper Tithonian, in association with ammonites that indicate the *Malbosiceras chaperi* Subzone of the *P. transitorius* Zone).

The cysts of *Prolixosphaeridium perforospineum* were found in two borehole sections and one outcrop: borehole R-1 Yunak (depth 1495 m, Ticha Formation, upper Tithonian, in association with calpionellids from the *Crassicollaria* Zone); borehole R-3 Yunak (depth 1695.5 m, Ticha Formation, middle Tithonian); and an outcrop at Mahala Popska near the town of Sevlievo (Zlataritsa–Cherni Osam Formation, upper Tithonian, in association with ammonites that indicate the *Malbosiceras chaperi* Subzone of the *P. transitorius* Zone).

***Occisucysta balios*–*Lithodinia bulloidea* Concurrent–range Subzone**

Name. This subzone is named after the two species with coincident occurrence whose ranges define it.
Stratigraphy. The subzone is characterized by the coincident concurrent ranges of *Occisucysta balios* Gitmez, 1970 emended Jan du Chêne *et al.*, 1986 (Dodekova, 1994, p. 42, pl. 10, figs 3–5), and

Lithodinia bulloidea (Cookson & Eisenack, 1960) Gocht, 1976 (Dodekova, 1994, p. 24, pl. 5, figs 1, 2, 5, 15). In addition, *Systematophora daveyi* Riding & Thomas, 1988 (Dodekova, 1994, p. 34, pl. 7, fig. 6), *Systematophora?* *prodigiosa* Dodekova (1994, p. 35, pl. 8, figs 3–6) and *Semicavidinium mitra* (Dürr, 1987) (Dodekova, 1994, p. 28, pl. 6, figs 5, 8–11, pl. 7, fig. 12) also occur, probably at upper levels of the subzone. The *Occisucysta balios*–*Lithodinia bulloidea* Concurrent–range Subzone corresponds to the middle Tithonian and the lowermost upper Tithonian and correlates with the total extent of the *Virgatosimoceras rothpletzi* Zone and the *Parapallasiceras* spp. Zone, but also extends into the lowermost part of the *P. transitorius* Zone (see Fig. 5). Unspecified upper levels of the subzone correlate with the calpionellid *Chitinoidea* Zone.

Distribution. *Systematophora daveyi*, *Semicavidinium mitra* and *Systematophora?* *prodigiosa* were recorded in the borehole section R-1 Yunak (depth 1605 m, Ticha Formation, middle Tithonian, in association with calpionellids from the *Chitinoidea* Zone).

***Prolixosphaeridium?* *foratun*–*Dichadogonyaulax culmula* Concurrent–range Subzone**

Name. The subzone is named after the two species with coincident occurrence whose ranges define it.

Stratigraphy. The subzone is characterized by the coincident concurrent ranges of *Prolixosphaeridium?* *foratun* Dodekova (1994, p. 26, pl. 5, figs 3, 4, 10, 13) and *Dichadogonyaulax culmula* (Norris, 1965) Loeblich & Loeblich, 1968 (Dodekova, 1994, p. 45, pl. 8, figs 13, 14). Additionally, *Leptodinium?* *ambiguiformis* Dodekova (1994, p. 39, pl. 12, figs 5, 8, 9–11; Fig. 6) and *Cribroperidinium* sp. *A sensu* Davey, 1982 (Dodekova, 1994, p. 37, pl. 9, figs 2, 3) were also recorded at lower levels of the subzone. The range of the subzone corresponds to most of the upper Tithonian (*P. transitorius* ammonite Zone, as well as calpionellid *Crassicollaria* Zone and *Calpionella* Zone, *C. alpina* Subzone) (see Fig. 5), but it can also extend into the Berriasian.

Distribution. *Prolixosphaeridium?* *foratun* was recorded in four borehole sections: R-3 Devetaki (depth 2546–2548 m, Kaspichan Formation, upper Tithonian); R-11 Zhitnitsa (depth 1713.8 m, Ticha Formation, upper Tithonian–Berriasian, in association with calpionellids of the *Calpionella* Zone, *C. alpina* Subzone); R-7 Sultantsi (depth 1707–1742 m, upper Tithonian, in association with calpionellids of the *Crassicollaria* Zone); and R-1

Yunak (depth 1495 m, Ticha Formation, upper Tithonian, in association with calpionellids of the *Crassicollaria* Zone). *Dichadogonyaulax culmula* was recorded in two borehole sections: R-10 Padina (depth 1656.6 m, Ticha-Kaspichan-Drinovo-Chernookovo Formation, upper Tithonian); and R-8 Sultantsi (depth 1795 m, Ticha Formation, upper Tithonian). *Leptodinium? ambiguiformis* was

recognized in numerous specimens from the borehole section R-7 Sultantsi (depth 1765 m, Ticha Formation, upper Tithonian, in association with calpionellids of the *Crassicollaria* Zone). *Cribroperidinium* sp. A was found in the borehole section R-1 Yunak (depth 1495 m, Ticha Formation, upper Tithonian, in association with calpionellids of the *Crassicollaria* Zone).

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